

Customers’ Attitude Towards Indane Gas in Srivilliputtur

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Abstract

Humanity faces a unique and far-reaching challenge. Our energy needs are growing as a result of continued population increases, economic growth, and individual fuel/energy consumption. At the same time, emissions from fuel wood and fossil fuels, the main energy source for heating in homes and powering our economies, are contributing to climate change and affecting the local air quality. Liquefied Petroleum Gas is used as fuel for thousands of applications. In developing countries the main benefits of LPG is in helping people to switch from unsustainable biomass use to a clean and safe cooking fuel. LPG’s domestic uses can never be ignored. It has played a revolutionary role when it comes to changing the face of domestic fuels used for heating and cooking. HPCL commenced marketing of LPG under the brand name “HP GAS”. The data is fully based on Primary & Secondary data collection. Four objectives are framed for this analysis. The statistical tools applied for this study are Pearson’s correlation coefficient, chi square test and ANOVA. Through this study the HP Gas Company is suggested to improve their service quality among the consumers.

Introduction

Humanity faces a unique and comprehensive challenge. Our energy need is growing as a result of continued population increases, economic growth and individual fuel/energy consumption. At the same time, emissions from fuel wood and fossil fuels, the main energy source for heating in houses and powering our economies, are contributing to climate change and affecting the local air quality. Now a day Indane is one of the largest packed-LPG brands in the world and has been conferred the coveted Consumer Super brand status by the Super brands Council of India. Having launched LPG marketing in the mid-70s, Indian Oil has been credited with bringing about a kitchen revolution, spreading warmth and cheer in millions of households with the introduction of the clean and efficient cooking fuel. Indane have led to a substantial improvement in the health of women, especially in rural areas by replacing smoky and unhealthy Chula.

Review of Literature

Mônica Cavalcanti Sá De Abreu and Jonatan César Lins (2010), in their article titled “A Demographic Analysis of Consumer Environmental Attitudes about Liquefied Petroleum Gas in Brazil” concluded that consumers think environmental and safety issues related to LPG are important but lack information on whether or not companies are taking action on these issues. LPG distributors have an opportunity to strengthen consumer relationships by disseminate practical information to the customer on the handling of LPG. It is of importance for companies to provide optimistic feedback on a regular basis in order to show costumers that they really are making a difference. Businesses which critically consider environmental issues may create a sustainable competitive advantage.

A. Vinayagamoorthy, C. Sankar and M.Sangeetha (2013), in their article titled “A Study on Service Quality Perception of Domestic LPG” concluded that in this the competitive environment, service quality has become the success mantra in all service sector. Keeping this in mind, this study has conducted at Salem city to discover the service quality of Indane gas. The results indicate that customers are not highly satisfied with the service provided by the Indane gas. So the company took some severe action to improve the service quality.

M. Dhanabhakym and T. Sumathi (2014), in their article titled “A Study on Customers Attitude and Satisfaction towards HP LPG in House Hold, Coimbatore” concluded that by seeing the overall customer service and the performance of the company, the results show that the consumers have positive attitude towards referring others to buy the HP LPG. This study emphasizes that the company wants to improve in customer care area, proper communication while booking and delivery through short message service (SMS). HP Gas Company should recognize the importance and needs of the customers.

Statement of the Problem

In the competitive era, the Indane gas company reform has deregulated the market to a great extent. It has become essential to design and execute the best customer oriented practices and to internalize them for providing better satisfaction to the customer through their employees. Customers’ service is not only the compliance with the Government’s policies or the mechanical adherence to the time frame of services. It is a philosophy and an attitude of professional commitment, which believes in the vital satisfaction or each customer ‘wants’. Service marketers have actually understood that competition can be well managed by differentiating through quality. Significance of service lies in customer service management. Hence, the present study is undertaken to analyse the customers’ attitude towards Indane Gas in Srivilliputtur.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To study the customers attitude towards Indane gas.
2. To analyse the problems faced by the customer and service provided by the company.
3. To offer suitable suggestions based upon the findings of the study.

Methodology

Data, which is a vital to this research, has collected through various resources. Both primary and secondary data have used in this study. Primary data is the first hand information, which has been collected through questionnaire from the sample customers in Srivilliputtur. The secondary data is a vital part of any research study or a project report as it provides information on key variables, which play a major part in the actual research. The sources of secondary data collected for this

study includes websites, journals, magazines, books and so on. The study is based on sampling method. To study the customer attitude towards Indane gas, 125 sample respondents were selected by adopting convenient sampling method from various areas in Srivilliputtur.

Customer Attitude

Customers Attitude has been understood as a scholarly predisposition, which plan positive or negative behavior consistently towards various objects of the world. Attitude influence the way we think and behave and are therefore vital for the marketers who study them to understand how a consumer behaves. Attitudes can be either of a high or low degree and the passion depends on the strength of conviction with which the person believes in them.

Table 1 Customers’ Attitude Towards Service Rendered By The Indane Gas

Sl. No	Particulars	SA (2)	A (1)	NO (0)	DA (-1)	SDA (-2)	Total	W Score	WAM
Connection									
1	Easy to get an application	52	48	9	14	2	125	134	1.07
2	Application cost is low	26	8	56	33	2	125	23	0.18
3	Document formalities are easy	32	12	43	27	11	125	27	0.22
4	Deposit is low	49	18	12	42	4	125	66	0.53
5	Dealers insist on buying stove from them	56	39	5	9	16	125	110	0.88
6	Quick connection	24	18	41	28	14	125	10	0.08
Cylinder									
7	Cost of cylinder is low	27	36	17	29	16	125	29	0.23
8	Time to book next cylinder is slow	25	27	33	16	24	125	13	0.10
9	Time to supply next cylinder is slow	45	23	33	20	4	125	85	0.68
10	Getting second cylinder is easy	33	27	28	17	20	125	36	0.29
Stove									
11	Cost of stove is low	26	27	29	24	19	125	17	0.14
12	Cost of spare parts are low	37	23	15	19	31	125	16	0.13
13	Quality of spare parts are good	24	28	35	20	18	125	20	0.16
14	Spare parts are always available	35	15	25	23	27	125	8	0.06
After Sales Service									
15	Indane gas ensures prompt services during the period of warranty	27	35	23	19	21	125	28	0.22
16	Indane gas provides service in time	31	27	10	34	23	125	9	0.07
17	The service charge are reasonable	19	36	25	27	18	125	11	0.09
18	The quality of service is good	43	17	14	26	25	125	27	0.21
19	Customers will get proper advice from the service centres for the maintenance	32	48	13	22	10	125	70	0.56
Repairs									
20	Repairs are rare	54	14	15	14	28	125	52	0.42

21	Repair calls responded quickly	27	37	18	32	11	125	37	0.30
22	Repairs done quickly	48	37	15	11	14	125	94	0.75
23	Repairs cost are low	37	23	15	18	32	125	15	0.12
24	Quality of repair is good	41	34	16	19	15	125	67	0.54
Deliveryman									
25	Delivers at the time when some one is available in the house	31	32	18	19	25	125	25	0.20
26	The behaviour is good	45	13	22	18	27	125	31	0.25
27	Checks the cylinder properly	39	31	16	24	15	125	55	0.44
28	Demands tips	33	22	10	36	24	125	4	0.03
Others									
29	Indane cooking gas is more economic than other kinds of domestic cooking fuel	28	28	17	27	25	125	7	0.06
30	Cooking becomes very simple and convenient if we done with Indane gas	36	31	10	10	33	125	27	0.22
31	Customers are treated well	37	28	15	21	24	125	33	0.26
32	It is a prestige to be a customer of Indane gas	35	23	15	28	24	125	17	0.14
33	The non-availability or scarcity of other kinds of fuel is the main reason for using Indane gas	41	34	16	23	11	125	71	0.57
34	Using Indane gas saves time	31	44	18	22	10	125	64	0.51
35	Cooking with Indane gas is out of risk	38	15	21	23	28	125	12	0.10
36	Food cooked in Indane gas is tasty	29	31	16	24	25	125	15	0.12
37	Environmental factors make it compulsory to use Indane gas	53	12	10	36	14	125	54	0.43

Source: Primary Data

Connection

The analysis revealed that the level of agreement towards connection was at the maximum of 1.07 points for 'Easy to get an application form', followed by 0.88 points for 'Dealers insist on buying stove from them', 0.53 points for 'Deposit is low', 0.22 points for 'Document formalities are easy', 0.18 point for 'Application cost is low' and 0.08 points for 'Quick connection'.

Cylinder

The analysis showed that the level of agreement towards cylinder was at the maximum of 0.68 points for 'Time to supply next cylinder is slow', followed by 0.29 points for 'Getting second cylinder is easy', 0.23 points for 'Cost of cylinder is low' and 0.10 points for 'Time to book next cylinder is slow'.

Stove

The analysis revealed that the level of agreement towards stove was at the maximum of 0.16 points for 'Quality of spare parts are good', followed by 0.14 points for 'Cost of stove is low', 0.13 points for 'Cost of spare parts are low' and 0.06 points for 'Spare parts are always available'.

After Sales Service

The analysis showed that the level of agreement towards after sales service was at the maximum of 0.56 points for ‘Customers will get proper advice from the service centres for the maintenance’, followed by 0.22 points for ‘Indane gas ensures prompt services during the period of warranty’, 0.21 points for ‘The quality of service is good’, 0.09 points for ‘The service charge are reasonable’ and 0.07 points for ‘Indane gas provides service in time’.

Repairs

The analysis revealed that the level of agreement towards repairs was at the maximum of 0.75 points for ‘Repairs done quickly’, followed by 0.54 points for ‘Quality of repair is good’, 0.42 points for ‘Repairs are rare’, 0.30 points for ‘Repair calls responded quickly’ and 0.12 points for ‘Repairs cost are low’.

Deliveryman

The analysis showed that the level of agreement towards delivery man was at the maximum of 0.44 points for ‘Checks the cylinder properly’, followed by 0.25 points for ‘The behaviour is good’, 0.20 points for ‘Delivers at the time when some one is available in the house’ and 0.03 points for ‘Demand tips’.

Others

The analysis showed that the level of agreement towards others was at the maximum of 0.57 points for ‘The non-availability or scarcity of other kinds of fuel is the main reason for using Indane gas’, followed by 0.51 points for ‘Using Indane gas saves time’, 0.43 points for ‘Environmental factors make it compulsory to use Indane gas’, 0.26 points for ‘Customers are treated well’, 0.22 points for ‘Cooking becomes very simple and convenient if we done with Indane gas’, 0.14 points for ‘It is a prestige to be a customer of Indane gas’, 0.12 points for ‘Food cooked in Indane gas is tasty’, 0.10 points for ‘Cooking with Indane gas is out of risk’ and 0.06 points for ‘Indane cooking gas is more economic than other kinds of domestic cooking fuel’.

Suggestions

The following are the suggestions to improve the services of Indane gas:

It is suggested that the Indane gas company should take some necessary action to improve their service quality by the way; they can introduce some additional dealers and provide constant service to the customers.

It is suggested that the company needs to develop in customer care area, proper communication while booking and delivery through short message service.

In order to avoid likely fire accidents, it is suggested that there should be periodical checking up of the cylinder.

Conclusion

Customers are the life blood for every business. It is necessary for a healthy business in creating new customers, keeping loyal customers, and developing referrals for future customers. In this competitive atmosphere, quality service has become the secret of success in all service sectors. As LPG has been moved towards buyers market, the Indane gas should afford better customer service than his competitors.

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